

A Correlational Study of Bronchoalveolar Lavage and Brushing Cytology with Bronchial Biopsy in the Diagnosis of Lung Malignancies

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Abstract:

Background: Lung cancer is a major public health concern in India as well as globally with high fatality rates. This study aims to compare the efficacy of bronchoalveolar lavage, bronchoalveolar brushing with biopsy findings in the diagnosis of lung carcinoma.

Methods: The study was a tertiary health care centre based cross sectional study conducted at the Department of Pathology at Sardar Patel Medical College and Associated Group of Hospitals, Bikaner over a period of two years between January 2022 and December 2023. All the bronchoalveolar lavage and bronchial brushing and bronchial biopsy specimens were examined.

Results: Brushing cytology has a sensitivity of 65.45% and bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) cytology has a sensitivity 43.64%. The most commonly reported carcinoma in our study was squamous cell carcinoma (61.82%) followed by small cell carcinoma (21.82%) and adenocarcinoma (14.54%).

Conclusion: Bronchial brushing emerges as an inexpensive and minimally invasive technique with a good diagnostic yield, exhibiting both high sensitivity and specificity, and outperforming

Keywords: Lung Carcinoma, Bronchial Brushing, Bronchoalveolar Lavage, Bronchial Biopsy.

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Introduction

Lung cancer is a major public health concern in India as well as globally with high fatality rates. In India, it accounts for 5.9% of all cancers and 8.1% of cancer-related deaths. [1] Lung cancer has been ranked the second leading cause of cancer in males and sixth leading cause in females in India. [2] Most patients of lung cancer are diagnosed when the disease is either locally advanced or metastasized making radical treatment difficult and most patients only receive palliative care. Hence, early diagnosis becomes necessary for patients to have more options for treatment and also to improve the rate of survival. Several studies have shown that early diagnosis, localisation and aggressive treatment can improve survival rate by 70-80%. [3]

Flexible fiberoptic bronchoscopy has an established role in the early diagnosis and localisation of lung cancer. The introduction of fiberoptic bronchoscopy transformed respiratory cytology and in the current world scenario, cytology plays a very important role in the early diagnosis of carcinoma lung.

Bronchoalveolar lavage is a minimally invasive procedure useful for diagnosing lung infections, bronchoalveolar hemorrhage, interstitial lung

diseases like idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and sarcoidosis, and detecting tumor cells. Bronchial brushings, first analyzed in 1973, are now used to diagnose airway mucosal abnormalities, nodules, masses, and sarcoidosis. [4]

The value and reliability of bronchoalveolar lavage and bronchial brushing cytology over histological diagnosis is still up for debate. This study aims to compare the efficacy of bronchoalveolar lavage, bronchoalveolar brushing with biopsy findings in the diagnosis of lung carcinoma.

Materials and Methods

The study was a tertiary health care centre based cross sectional study conducted at the Department of Pathology at Sardar Patel Medical College and Associated Group of Hospitals, Bikaner over a period of two years between January 2022 and December 2023. All the bronchoalveolar lavage and bronchial brushing and bronchial biopsy specimens were collected by the chest physician at Department of Chest and Tuberculosis, S.P. Medical College and PBM Hospital Bikaner and sent to the Department of Pathology. All specimens that fulfilled the inclusion criteria were included in the study

Inclusion Criteria:

All adequate and representative specimens of bronchoalveolar lavage, bronchial brushing and lung biopsy received at the Department of Pathology.

Exclusion Criteria:

Inadequate specimens

Autolysed and necrosed specimens

Specimens with improper record

Bronchoalveolar lavage specimens were received in aliquots of 40-50 ml which was then centrifuged and smeared onto slides. Bronchial brushing was received as air dried and wet fixed smears. The slides were then stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin.

The biopsy specimens were preserved in 10% formalin and allowed to fix for 24 hours. Routine processing was done and hematoxylin and eosin stained sections were obtained. Special staining was done wherever needed.

All collected data was entered into Microsoft excel worksheet. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 20.0 software. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm SD and categorical variables were expressed as percentages. Chi square test was used to find association between smoking habit and histopathology diagnosis. P value less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Diagnostic indices (Sensitivity, Specificity, Positive predictive value, Negative predictive value) of BAL and Brushing were calculated using following standard formula

Results**Table 1: results of bronchoalveolar lavage and brushing cytology**

Sample	True positive	True negative	False positive	False negative	Total
BAL	24	47	0	31	102
BRUSHING	36	47	0	19	102

Sensitivity of brushing cytology was 65.45%; while that of bronchoalveolar lavage cytology was only 43.64%. Specificity of brushing cytology was 100% and that of bronchoalveolar lavage cytology was also 100%. Accuracy of brush cytology was 81.37% while that of bronchoalveolar lavage cytology was 69.61%. (Table 2)

Table 2: indices of bronchoalveolar lavage and brushing cytology

INDICES	BAL	BRUSHING
Sensitivity	43.64%	65.45%
Specificity	100.0%	100.0%
Positive Predictive Value	100.0%	100.0%
Negative Predictive Value	60.26%	71.21%
Accuracy	69.61%	81.37%

On biopsy, 34 cases were classified as squamous cell carcinoma, 8 cases as adenocarcinoma, 12 cases as small cell carcinoma and there was 1 case of large cell carcinoma. Out of the 24 true positive cases given on bronchoalveolar lavage, 8 cases

A total of 102 cases of suspected lung cancer were included in the study over a study period of 2 years. All three techniques (Bronchoalveolar lavage, Bronchial brush cytology, Bronchial biopsy) were used simultaneously in all patients under study. Out of these 102 cases, 55 tested positive on biopsy for carcinoma. Rest of the cases showed non specific inflammatory or no significant pathology and were considered as negative for carcinoma.

In our study, majority of cases of lung carcinoma were seen in the 61-70 years age group followed by 51-60 years age group with a mean age of 62.47 \pm 7.14 years. Majority of the cases of lung cancer were diagnosed in males accounting for 89.1% and females accounted for 10.9% and the male:female ratio was 8.6:1.

In our study, 70.6% of the suspected patients were smokers. The biopsy positive group had a statistically significant (P value <0.05) higher proportion of smoker than negative group. Out of those that tested for positive for cancer 45(81.8%) were smokers and 10(18.2%) were non-smokers and among those that tested negative the total number of smokers were 27(57.5%) and non-smokers were 20(42.5%).

In the comparison of cytology and biopsy, bronchoalveolar lavage cytology showed 24 true positive cases and 47 true negative cases, as confirmed by biopsy. Moreover, 0 cases were diagnosed as false positive and 31 cases as false negative by bronchoalveolar lavage. Brushing cytology showed 36 true positive cases and 47 true negative cases with 0 cases as false positive and 19 cases as false negative. (Table 1)

were classified as squamous cell carcinoma, 4 cases as adenocarcinoma, 4 cases as small cell carcinoma and 1 case as large cell carcinoma and all these were correlating with the histopathological diagnosis. 7 cases out of the 24 could not be

subtyped and were only reported as “malignant cells seen” or as “positive for malignancy.” Out of the 36 true positive cases given on bronchial brush cytology, 22 cases were classified as squamous cell carcinoma, 4 cases as adenocarcinoma, 7 cases as small cell carcinoma and 1 case as large cell carcinoma and were correlating with the

histopathological diagnosis. Only 2 out of the 36 true positive cases were reported as “positive for malignancy.”(Table 3) The highest typing accuracy was observed for squamous cell carcinoma(64.7%) on brushing cytology and for small cell carcinoma on bronchoalveolar lavage cytology.

Table 3: comparison of cytological diagnosis with histopathological diagnosis

Histopathological diagnosis	Number of cases diagnosed on BAL	Number of cases diagnosed on BB	Total number of cases on biopsy
Squamous cell carcinoma	8(23.5%)	22(64.7%)	34
Adenocarcinoma	4(50%)	4(50%)	8
Large cell carcinoma	1(100%)	1(100%)	1
Small cell carcinoma	4(33.33%)	7(58.3%)	12

The most commonly reported carcinoma in our study was squamous cell carcinoma(61.82%) followed by small cell carcinoma(21.82%) and adenocarcinoma(14.54%). We had only case of large cell carcinoma.

Image 1: Bronchial biopsy: Large cell carcinoma (40X, H&E)

Image 2: Bronchial biopsy: Adenocarcinoma (40X, H&E)

Image 3: Bronchoalveolar lavage: Small cell carcinoma- group of cells showing nuclear moulding, salt and pepper chromatin (40X, H&E)

Discussion:

Lung cancer diagnosis in respiratory practice is a challenge to doctors all over the world. India, with a current population of 1.67 billion, is no exception in this regard. With increasing awareness among physicians and better diagnostic modalities, an increase in carcinoma lung incidence is noted. Early detection and treatment are essential for reducing mortality.

In our study we include all those cases suspected to have lung cancer and where all three investigative techniques- bronchoalveolar lavage, bronchial brushing and biopsy were used. A total of 102 cases were included - out of this 55 cases were "malignant" where the comparison between bronchoalveolar lavage, bronchial brushing and biopsy was done. The rest of 47 cases were reported as reactive, tuberculosis or inconclusive and were considered as "non malignant"

In our study, the majority of cases of lung carcinoma were seen in the 61-70 years with the mean age being 62.47 ± 7.14 . The male:female ratio was 8.6:1. A study done in north western Rajasthan by Kumar et al [5] to estimate the incidence of lung cancer reported the most common age group as 61-70 years with males being the more common gender accounting for 87.37% with the male:female ratio being 6.9:1 which is similar to our study.

In our study, 70.6% of the suspected patients were smokers. The biopsy positive group had a statistically significant (P value <0.05) higher proportion of smoker than negative group. Similar findings have been reported by Rohit Ravindra Chordia et al [6] (63.95%) and by Singh N et al [7] (76.9%).

In our study, sensitivity of bronchoalveolar lavage was 43.64%(Table 2). Most studies report the

sensitivity for bronchoalveolar lavage between 21% to 78% [8] and our results are within this range. Our results were comparable to that of Gaur DS et al[9] who reported the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of bronchoalveolar lavage as 39.40%, 89.6% and 71.40% respectively.

For bronchial brushing cytology, the sensitivity in most studies range from 21% to 93% and our results for sensitivity of brushing cytology fall within this range.(Table 2) Our results were also comparable to that done by Gaur DS et al [9] and Sareen R et al[10]. Gaur DS et al [9] reported the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of bronchial brushing as 87.3%, 89.6% and 93.9% respectively. Sareen R et al [10] reported the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of bronchial brushing as 77.78%, 100% and 84% respectively. In our study we did not encounter any false positives and these results are in concordance with that of Sareen R et al [10]

As far as typing of the cancer is concerned, using the bronchoalveolar lavage 17/24 out of cases were correctly classified into specific subtypes. Bronchial brushing was a better diagnostic modality for typing of cancer as compared to bronchoalveolar lavage. On bronchial brushing 34 out of 36 positive cases were classified into specific subtypes. Several other studies have also shown also reported brushing to be a better modality for subtyping as compared to bronchoalveolar lavage because of its better demonstration of cellular details. [9]

The variability in values in different studies could stem from multiple factors - some of which include difference in techniques used to collect the sample, the processing of sample and preparation of slide as well as variation in the interpretation of cytological appearances. The bronchial brushing technique scores an advantage over bronchoalveolar lavage

because it effectively scrapes cells from the surface of suspicious lesions using a brush that is inserted through bronchoscope. [9]

Conclusion

In a country like ours, with an increasing population and finite resources, it seems prudent to utilise bronchoscopic techniques for the timely diagnosis of lung cancer. We can conclude that bronchoalveolar lavage and bronchial brushing cytology are very useful in diagnosing lung malignancies. These cytology specimens can yield excellent diagnoses when correlated with good clinical history and imaging studies. Bronchial brushing emerges as an inexpensive and minimally invasive technique with a good diagnostic yield, exhibiting both high sensitivity and specificity, and outperforming bronchoalveolar lavage in the cytological diagnosis of lung cancer. However, biopsy still remains the gold standard for accurate diagnosis and typing.

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